

Tips for a Hitch Free Examination Invigilation

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Introduction

- Examination Invigilator is responsible for ensuring that exams are conducted in an **appropriate manner** within the allotted time frame and in accordance with any exam **rules and procedure**.
- The goal of an invigilator should be to prevent the students from committing any punishable examination misconduct, only when students maneuvered their way into committing the acts then the invigilator would have no alternative rather than to enforce the law!

Functions of Invigilator

As an important component of exam management, he has the following functions

- Ensure conduct of the examination.
- Maintains exams **integrity**.
- Ensures that no unfair or **nefarious activities** are utilized during exams.
- Provide **level of Protection** to the University.
- Protect **self integrity** and that of the University

Work of an Invigilator.....

- Receives all **examination materials** and delivers same to the examination hall.
- Screens and allow **only eligible** students in to the hall.
- Distributes singed Examination Booklets to **only eligible** students.
- Issuance of question paper and assist with any clarification when needed.

.....Work of an Invigilator.....

- **Signing with dates**, of students' examination card within the spaces provided.
- While signing, invigilators are advised to compare Images on ID cards, Examination cards with the face of the person writing the examination to avoid **impersonation**.
- This can only be achieved if invigilators follow **seat by seat** to sign examination cards. This can be done wisely without unnecessarily distracting the students.

.....Work of an Invigilator.

- Monitor any suspicious movements, actions or behavior by students, as this may be preparatory to committing **exams malpractice**.
- Ensure students only **sign in** before they are giving exams material and **sign out** only when they are done with the exams and have submitted!

Tips

- Never allow student to **sign in and sign out** at the same time. This may be indicting to the invigilator!
- Never allow students that are **not supposed to be in your hall** to write any examination, this may also be indicting to the invigilator.
- Don't allow student to submit **earlier than normal**, keep them waiting until it is middle of the examination or towards the end.
- Always collect submitted booklets **hand to hand** and let them be in your custody, never put them on the flow for the student to freely submit, booklets can easily be **stolen, replaced** or **tempered** with.

...Tips...

- Check the students' signature on their examination Cards and compare with the one on their attendance sheet if you are **suspecting Impersonation**.
- Always move around the examination hall **silently and tactically**, students nowadays have different ways of introduction relevant materials into the examination hall.

...Tips...

- In case you see any examination malpractice act by establishing exhibit using Camera, booklet or any relevant materials,
- Ask the student to fill the **relevant form**, if he refuses, on the form, fill the area meant for you and report the case to Chairman faculty examination Misconduct Committee.
- Ensure you count the number of booklets submitted by students to see if they tally with what you have collected earlier. Don't dismiss the student from the hall until you have an **equal number** on the attendance sheet!

Thanks

for

your

time.